

THE CONDENSATION OF α -SUBSTITUTED ACETOACETATES WITH PHENOLS. PART VI. THE CONDENSATION OF PHENOLS WITH ETHYL ACETOSUCCINATE

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The Pechmann condensation of several phenols with ethyl acetosuccinate in presence of different condensing agents has been studied with a view to finding the effect of $-\text{CH}_2\text{COOEt}$ as α -substituent on the course of the reaction. Reactive phenols like resorcinol, orcinol, etc., easily undergo the condensation. Various coumarin-3-acetic acids and their derivatives have been synthesised. Of the less reactive phenols, *m*-cresol and β -naphthol condense with the formation of the corresponding coumarin derivatives.

In extension of the previous work on the condensation of α -substituted acetoacetates (with α -substituents other than alkyl) with phenols (Shah and Shah, *Ber.*, 1938, 71, 2075; Shah, *J. Univ. Bombay*, 1939, 8, 205; Kulkarni, Alimchandani and Shah, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 18, 113, 123; Shah and Kulkarni, *J. Univ. Bombay*, 1941, 10, 86), the present investigation was undertaken with a view to study systematically the effect of carboethoxy-methyl (CH_2COOEt) group as an α -substituent in the acetoacetate molecule on its reactivity in the Pechmann condensation. This communication describes the results of the condensation of ethyl acetosuccinate with several phenols under the conditions of Pechmann and Simonis reactions as well as in the presence of other condensing agents.

Condensation of ethyl acetosuccinate with reactive phenols like resorcinol, pyrogallol, orcinol, α -naphthol and phloroglucinol.—The condensation of resorcinol with ethyl acetosuccinate in presence of sulphuric acid has been described by several investigators (Bannerjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 777; Dey and Sankaranarayanan, *ibid.*, p. 819; Chakravarti, *ibid.*, 1935, 12, 538). We have now further investigated this condensation in the presence of (1) aluminium chloride, (2) phosphorus oxychloride and (3) phosphoric anhydride. In all cases, the coumarin derivative identical with one obtained by using sulphuric acid is obtained. 7-Hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-3-acetic acid is obtained directly in good yield, with aluminium chloride as condensing agent, the expected ester being hydrolysed during the reaction. Phosphoric anhydride gives the same coumarin as its ester (I; R = H) in very poor yield; while phosphorus oxychloride produces the same ester (I, R = H) in excellent yield. It is noteworthy that in this as well as in subsequent condensations described here, the oxychloride has been found to be a very efficient condensing agent giving the maximum yields of the condensation products.

Ethyl 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-3-acetate (I, R = H) on hydrolysis gives the acid identical with the acid obtained by aluminium chloride method. This acid is stable and cannot be decarboxylated by heating above its melting point. However, the de-carboxylation is effected by quinoline-copper method, using its acetyl derivative. The product obtained is identical with 7-hydroxy-3 : 4-dimethylcoumarin, the de-acetylation having occurred during the reaction.

Ethyl 7-acetoxy-4-methylcoumarin-3-acetate on Fries migration with aluminium chloride gives 7-hydroxy-8-acetyl-4-methylcoumarin-3-acetic acid (II) identical with the acid obtained by the hydrolysis of the condensation product of 2-acetyl-resorcinol with ethyl acetosuccinate.

Orcinol on condensation with ethyl acetosuccinate in the presence of phosphorus oxychloride gives an excellent yield of ethyl 5-hydroxy-4 : 7-dimethyl-coumarin-3-acetate (III ; R = CH₃), from which the corresponding coumarin-3-acetic acid is obtained by hydrolysis.

Pyrogallol on similar condensation gives ethyl 7 : 8-dihydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-3-acetate (I, R = OH). Sulphuric acid as condensing agent has been found to hydrolyse the ester giving directly the acid (*cf.*, Chakravarti, *loc. cit.*). Aluminium chloride does not give any condensation product. Attempts to decarboxylate the acid as well as the Fries transformation of 7 : 8-diacetoxy-coumarin derivative have been unsuccessful.

The condensation of *o*-naphthol has been studied in presence of sulphuric acid, phosphorus oxychloride and pentoxide as well as aluminium chloride. In all cases, 4-methyl-*o*-naphthapyrone-3-acetic acid or its ethyl ester identical with those of the previous workers (Bannerjee, *loc. cit.* Dey and Sankaranarayanan, *loc. cit.*) is obtained.

Phloroglucinol condenses smoothly in presence of sulphuric acid (60%) as well as phosphorus oxychloride. The acid is found to hydrolyse the ester giving the corresponding acid; the oxychloride gives an excellent yield of ethyl 5 : 7-dihydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-3-acetate (III, R = OH) which on hydrolysis gives the corresponding coumarin-3-acetic acid.

The coumarin-3-acetic acids described here are very stable and are not easily decarboxylated in contrast to coumarin-4-acetic acids which easily lose carbon dioxide on heating (Dey and Row, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 1, 107, 22 *et seq.*). These acids do not react with aromatic aldehydes according to Knoevenagel reaction. An explanation in terms of induced alternate polarities for the reduced reactivity of coumarin-3-acetic acids (Bannerjee, *loc. cit.*) satisfactorily explains the behaviour of these acids studied in this investigation.

m-Cresol condenses with ethyl acetosuccinate with sulphuric acid as condensing agent. It is interesting to note that the change of temperature affects the condensation considerably. Ethyl 4 : 7-dimethylcoumarin-3-acetate (IV) may be obtained by keeping the reaction mixture well cooled. If the temperature is not properly kept down or the condensation carried out in summer months, a product, m.p. 135°, identical with 4 : 7-dimethylcoumarin, is obtained. It is noteworthy that the substituent is totally eliminated under the experimental conditions. A similar elimination of -CH₃.COOEt has also been observed in case of methyl β -resorcyate condensation (*see next paper*). Neither phosphorus oxychloride nor pentoxide could affect the condensation, unchanged cresol being obtained.

β -Naphthol gives on condensation in presence of sulphuric acid (but not in presence of phosphorus oxychloride or phosphorous pentoxide) 4-methyl- β -naphthapyrone-3-acetic acid identical with that of Dey and Sankaranarayanan (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 825). β -Naphthapyrone-3-acetic acid cannot be decarboxylated.

o-Cresol, *p*-cresol, quinol, phenol and catechol do not undergo condensation with ethyl-acetosuccinate.

(III)

(IV)

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Condensation of Resorcinol with Ethyl Acetosuccinate: Formation of 7-Hydroxy-4-methyl-coumarin-3-acetic acid and its Ethyl Ester.

(i) Resorcinol (5 g.) was mixed with ethyl acetosuccinate (10 g.) and phosphorus oxychloride (3 c.c.) gradually added with stirring and cooling. After sometime the mixture solidified; it was left at room temperature overnight. It was treated with cold water and the solid crystallised from alcohol as needles, m.p. 163°, yield nearly theoretical. Bannerjee (*loc. cit.*) and Dey and Sankaranarayanan (*loc. cit.*) give m.p. 162° and 163° respectively; mixed m.p. with the ester obtained by using sulphuric acid as a condensing agent according to the above authors was undepressed.

(ii) The condensation was carried out in presence of P_2O_5 (20 g.) (*cf.* Chakravarti, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 538). The product obtained in low yield was identical with the above ester, m.p. and mixed m.p. 163°.

The acetyl derivative crystallised from alcohol as shining plates, m.p. 98°.

The benzoyl derivative crystallised from alcohol and then from chloroform-benzine mixture as shining needles, m.p. 138°. Bannerjee (*loc. cit.*) gives m.p. 127°.

(iii) To a solution of aluminium chloride (5.5 g., 2 mols.) in dry nitrobenzene (30 c.c.), resorcinol (3 g., 1 mol.) and the ester (6 g., 1 mol.) were added and the mixture, protected from moisture by $CaCl_2$ guard tube, was heated on an oil-bath for 1 hour. Copious hydrochloric acid fumes were evolved. After the reaction subsided, the mixture was cooled and distilled in steam after adding ice and concentrated hydrochloric acid (10 c.c.). The residual liquid was freed from some tarry matter and on cooling it deposited needle-shaped crystals, m.p. 265-66°; mixed m.p. with the acid obtained by the hydrolysis of the ester was undepressed, yield 8.5 g. Both the acid and the ester dissolve in alkaline solution with blue fluorescence. The acetyl derivative, prepared by acetic anhydride and a drop of sulphuric acid, crystallised from hot water, m.p. 199-200°. (Found: Equiv., 274.8. $C_{14}H_{12}O_4$ requires Equiv., 276).

The benzoyl derivative crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 190-91°. (Found: C, 67.4; H, 4.2. $C_{17}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 67.45; H, 4.14 per cent).

Decarboxylation of the Acid.—7-Acetoxy-4-methylcoumarin-3-acetic acid (1 g.) was mixed with quinoline (15 c.c.), copper-bronze (0.3 g.) and refluxed for nearly 45 minutes with a low flame. Copper was removed, the filtrate mixed with excess of dilute hydrochloric acid and extracted with ether; the ethereal extract washed with sodium bicarbonate solution, the ethereal layer separated, dried and ether removed. The brown solid was dissolved in dilute sodium hydroxide, filtered and the filtrate acidified; the solid crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 254°, mixed m.p. with authentic sample unchanged. The acetyl derivative melts at 164°. Pechmann and Duisberg (*Ber.*, 1883, 16, 2119) give m.p. 165°.

Fries Transformation.—Ethyl 7-acetoxy-4-methylcoumarin-3-acetate (2 g.) was intimately mixed with aluminium chloride (7.8 g.) and heated on an oil-bath at 120-25° for 2 hours. It was then cooled and treated with ice-cold water acidified with hydrochloric acid. The solid was collected and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 256-57°. The product was identical with 7-hydroxy-8-acetyl-4-methylcoumarin-3-acetic acid (*vide* next paper).

The acid dissolves in alkali with yellowish colour without any fluorescence and gives red colour with alcoholic ferric chloride.

Condensation of Orcinol: Formation of Ethyl 5-hydroxy-4 : 7-dimethylcoumarin-3-acetate.—Anhydrous orcinol (2 g.) was condensed with ethyl acetosuccinate (3.5 g.) in presence of phosphorus oxychloride (2 c.c.). It was then worked up as before. The product crystallised from

alcohol as needles, m.p. 206°, yield 3 g. (Found: C, 64.8; H, 5.5. Calc. for $C_{11}H_{11}O_2$: C, 65.2; H, 5.8 per cent). Chakravarti (*loc. cit.*) gives m.p. 198-200°. The same condensation was repeated in presence of sulphuric acid and the product was obtained in less yield. It dissolves in alkali solution with non-fluorescent yellow colour.

The acetyl derivative crystallised from alcohol as needles, m.p. 91-92°. (Found: C, 64.0; H, 5.9. $C_{11}H_{11}O_2$ requires C, 64.15; H, 5.7 per cent).

5-Hydroxy-4:7-dimethylcoumarin-3-acetic Acid.—The above ester (1 g.) was boiled with 2N-NaOH (20 c.c.) on a water-bath for 15 minutes; it was cooled, acidified and the solid collected and crystallised from alcohol as lustrous plates, m.p. 270°. (Found: Equiv., 120. $C_{12}H_{12}O_3$ requires Equiv., 248). Evidently the pyrone ring has opened and the acid titrates as dibasic acid.

The acetyl derivative crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 183-84°. (Found: C, 62.0; H, 4.9. $C_{12}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 62.1; H, 4.8 per cent).

Condensation of Pyrogallol: Formation of 7:8-Dihydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-3-acetic Acid and its Ethyl Ester.

(i) Pyrogallol (4 g.) was mixed with ethyl aceto-succinate (7 g.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (20 c.c.) slowly added with cooling under tap; the mixture left overnight and then poured into cold water with stirring. No solid separated. On scratching the sides of the beaker, the solid began to come down slowly; it was collected after some time and crystallised from dilute acetone as needles, m.p. 240° (dried sample, m.p. 270°). (Found: C, 57.8; H, 4.1. $C_{12}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 57.6; H, 4.1 per cent). The acid dissolves in alkali and concentrated sulphuric acid with lemon-yellow colour. The acid was also obtained by the hydrolysis of the ester obtained below.

The acetyl derivative crystallised from dilute acetic acid, m.p. 224-25°. (Found: C, 57.3; H, 4.1. $C_{12}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 57.5; H, 4.2 per cent).

(ii) To prevent hydrolysis, the above condensation was repeated at lower temperature by keeping it in ice. The product obtained crystallised from dilute acetone as needles, m.p. 206°, yield 1 g. (Found: C, 60.4; H, 5.4. $C_{12}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 60.44; H, 5.04 per cent). Chakravarti (*loc. cit.*) gives m.p. 186°.

The ester dissolves in alkali with deep orange colour and gives with alcoholic ferric chloride green colour.

(iii) An excellent yield of the above ester was obtained by carrying out the above condensation with phosphorus oxychloride as condensing agent.

The acetyl derivative crystallised from alcohol as fine needles, m.p. 123-24°. (Found: C, 60.2; H, 5.2. $C_{12}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 59.7; H, 5.0 per cent).

Condensation of Phloroglucinol: Formation of 5:7-Dihydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-3-acetic Acid and its Ethyl Ester.—Anhydrous phloroglucinol (2 g.), ethyl aceto-succinate (3.5 g.) and phosphorus oxychloride (2 c.c.) were mixed with cooling under tap, and left overnight. The mixture was found solidified. It was worked up as before. The solid crystallised from alcohol as needles, m.p. 250°, yield about 4 g. (Found: C, 60.1; H, 4.95. $C_{14}H_{14}O_6$ requires C, 60.4; H, 5.03 per cent). It dissolves in alkali and concentrated sulphuric acid with greenish colour.

The acetyl derivative crystallised from alcohol as lustrous needles, m.p. 114-15°. (Found: C, 59.5; H, 4.83. $C_{14}H_{14}O_6$ requires C, 59.7; H, 5.0 per cent).

Hydrolysis of the Ester.—The ester (1 g.) was heated with 2N-NaOH (20 c.c.) for 20 minutes on a water-bath. It was then acidified; the solid crystallised from boiling water to which few drops of alcohol were added, m.p. above 285°. (Found: C, 57.5; H, 4.1. $C_{12}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 57.6; H, 4.0 per cent). The same acid was directly obtained by condensing phloroglucinol with sulphuric acid (80%) as condensing agent.

The acetyl derivative crystallised from alcohol as needles, m.p. 169-70°. (Found: C, 57.4; H, 4.3. $C_{15}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 57.5; H, 4.2 per cent).

Condensation of α -Naphthol: Formation of 4-Methyl- α -naphthopyrone-3-acetic Acid and its Ethyl Ester.

α -Naphthol was condensed in presence of different condensing agents as before; the results are summarised below.

Condensing agent.	Product obtained.	Remarks.
Conc. H_2SO_4	Ethyl 4-methyl- α -naphthopyrone-3-acetate, m.p. 141°	Dannerjee (<i>loc. cit.</i>) gives m.p. 137°. Very low yield.
P_2O_5	" "	"
H_2SO_4 (80%)	4-Methyl- α -naphthopyrone-3-acetic acid, m.p. 253-254°.	(Found: Equiv., 262. $C_{16}H_{14}O_4$ requires Equiv. 268).
$AlCl_3$	" "	"
$POCl_3$	" "	A coloured pasty mass was obtained which was worked up, yield 1.5 g. from a g. α -naphthol.

Condensation of m-Cresol: Formation of Ethyl 4:7-Dimethylcoumarin-3-acetate.—*m-Cresol* (5 g.) and ethyl aceto-succinate (10 g.) were mixed and concentrated sulphuric acid (20 c.c.) slowly added with cooling in ice. The mixture was left overnight in a vessel containing ice. It was then worked up by adding ice-water and the solid collected and crystallised from alcohol as needles, m.p. 106°, yield 3 g. (Found: C, 69.0; H, 5.9. $C_{18}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 69.2; H, 6.1 per cent).

4:7-Dimethylcoumarin-3-acetic Acid.—The ester (1 g.) was hydrolysed by heating on a water-bath with 2N-NaOH (20 c.c.). It was cooled and acidified and the solid separating crystallised from boiling water as fine lustrous needles, m.p. 193-94°. (Found: Equiv., 233.3. $C_{18}H_{18}O_4$ requires Equiv., 232).

Condensation of β -Naphthol: Formation of 4-Methyl- β -naphthopyrone-3-acetic Acid.—The mixture of β -naphthol (4 g.) and ethyl aceto-succinate (7 g.) was treated with concentrated sulphuric acid (12 c.c.) with cooling and left overnight. It was worked up as before. The substance crystallised from dilute alcohol as yellowish needles, m.p. 199°, yield 3 g. (Found: Equiv., 273. $C_{18}H_{18}O_4$ requires Equiv., 268). Dey and Sankaranarayanan (*loc. cit.*) give the same melting point.

The ethyl ester crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 101°.

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